

A Prospective Comparative Study On Small Bites Versus Large Bites Stitch For Fascial Closure Of Midline Abdominal Incisions In Patients Undergoing Emergency Laparotomy For Peptic Perforation Peritonitis

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Abstract

Aim: To compare the outcome of midline abdominal wound closure after a small tissue bites versus a large tissue bite.

Materials and Methods: A prospective randomized study was conducted in JLN Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer, from June 2022 to June 2024, for abdominal surgical problems requiring emergency laparotomy in the General Surgical ward and emergency ward. Patients were aged 12 years and above and of both sexes. Patients were randomized to wound closure with either a small or large tissue bites by lottery method into group A and group B. Group A (n=40): abdominal wall closed by Using Small Tissue Bites technique. Small tissue bites were placed at least 5 mm from the wound edge 5 mm apart. In Group B (n=40) the abdominal wall was closed by using the large tissue bites technique. Large tissue bites were placed 10 mm from the wound edge and 10 mm apart, and included only the aponeurosis in the stitches with or without the peritoneum.

Results: In this study mean age in Group A (Small Bite) is 47.6+17.95 years and in Group B (Large Bite) 47.5+15.29 years. 6 patients in Group A and 16 patients in Group B developed SSI. When comparing both the groups, the p value was 0.910 (NS). Wound dehiscence developed in 4 patients (10%) in Group A and in 5 patients (12.5%) in Group B. When comparing both groups, the p value was 0.630 (NS). Incisional hernia developed in 3 patients in Group A while 8 patients in Group B developed incisional hernia. When comparing both the groups the p-value was 0.782 (NS). In Group A, the ratio of mean SL to WL was less than or equal to 4.5: 1 it was in 17cases (42.5%) and in Group B, it was in 21 cases (52.5%). In Group B, the ratio of mean SL to WL was more than 4.5: 1 it was in 23 cases (57.5%), and in Group B, it was in 19 cases (47.5%), and the p-value was 0.3704 (NS). In Group A, time of fascial closure less than and equal to 10 minutes it was in 4 cases (10%) and in Group B it was in 32 cases (80%) and In Group A, time of facial closure more than 10 minutes it was in 36 cases (90%) and in Group B it was in 8 cases (20%), The mean time in small bite group was 12.8+1.86 and in large bite group it was 9.25+1.48 mins. The p-value is 0.0138 (Sig.)

Conclusion: The small bite suture technique offers several significant advantages over the large bite suture technique for fascial closure in midline abdominal incision in terms of post-operative complications such as Surgical Site infection, Wound Dehiscence, Incisional Hernia, post-operative pain and duration of hospital stay.

Keywords: small bites, large bite, suture technique, peptic perforation peritonitis.

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Introduction

The abdominal cavity has correctly been compared to Pandora's Box. Innumerable processes are simultaneously at work to maintain a physiological milieu compatible with life. In our country, even after advancements in imaging studies, many abdominal

diseases still require exploratory laparotomy in emergency situations. Midline incision is commonly used in exploratory laparotomies. It provides relatively quick (taking on an average five to seven minutes) and wide access to the abdominal cavity,

all quadrants of the abdomen and can be made with minimal damage to muscles, nerves and blood supply as these structures do not cross the midline. [1] The ideal wound closure provides strength and a barrier to infection. To achieve this goal, one should follow the principles of wound closure that is closure should be fast, efficient, performed without tension or ischemia, technically easier for surgeons and anesthesiologists. [2] A low tension of the suture line, sufficient collagen deposition, adequate blood supply and the absence of infection are prerequisites for undisturbed wound healing. [3] However, wound infection, seroma formation, burst abdomen and incisional hernia remain complications after laparotomy with reported incidences varying between 2% to 20%. The risk of developing complications are related to patient factors such as male sex, local wound infection, obesity, the use of glucocorticoids, hypoalbuminemia, anemia and emergency operations and operative factors such as postoperative infection. Certain factors that can be controlled by the surgeon are the choice of suture material and technique. [4] Surgical site infection (SSI) following abdominal closure is a common complication and is associated with an increased risk of wound dehiscence and incisional hernia, which can lead to negative outcomes such as increased reoperation rates. [5] SSI can occur after laparotomy, especially in an emergency setting. Dehiscence is a sequela of wound infection usually occurring 7 to 10 days postoperatively, but on rare occasions may occur even after 20 days postoperatively [6]. Of the known risk factors involved in incisional hernia development, surgical technique and suture material are the only factors directly controlled by the surgeon [7]. An association between the large bite technique and SSI has also been found and one study found that the rate of SSI could be halved when the small bite technique was employed. It has been suggested that the larger amount of surrounding tissue compressed in a large stitch bite may become necrotic, therefore predisposing to infection. [8] Study showed that a short stitch length has a lower risk of surgical site infection, wound dehiscence and incisional hernia [9]. However, in a recent experimental study that also considered the effect of the suture length (SL) to wound length (WL) ratio, stitches placed 5 mm from the wound edge produced a stronger wound after 4 days when inflammatory changes were at their peak compared with stitches placed at least 10 mm from the wound edge [10]. However, a larger bite incorporates tissue that offers no tensile strength, allowing the suture material to cut through and loosen the closure. A smaller bite aims to precisely grab only the fascia, the tissue that provides the tensile strength. A small bite versus a large bite was studied in the Netherlands (the STITCH Trial) and demonstrated an 8% absolute reduction in the occurrence of incisional hernia at one year in the small bite group. The small bite technique should become the standard clinical practice

closure technique for midline incisions [10]. Therefore, factors that may be expected to increase the strength of the wound and reduce tension on the surrounding tissue have been found to reduce dehiscence rates. Among these factors, one is the suture to wound length ratio and in cases where the ratio is >4:1, dehiscence rates are very rare. [11,12]

Aims and Objectives:

To Compare the Outcome of Midline Abdominal Wound Closure after using a small tissue bites versus a large tissue bite with reference to (i) Surgical Site Infection, (ii) Wound Dehiscence and (iii) Incisional hernia

Material and Methods

A prospective randomized study was conducted in JLN Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer, from June 2022 to June 2024, for abdominal surgical problems requiring emergency laparotomy in the General Surgical ward and emergency ward. Patients were aged 12 years and above and both sexes. Patients who provided consent for emergency laparotomy for peptic perforation were included in this study. Patients with comorbid conditions such as immunocompromised status, cancer chemotherapy, immunotherapy, long term steroids and diabetes, anemic patients and those who underwent a previous midline incision, patients with pre-existing abdominal wall hernia laparotomies for any other cause were excluded.

Patients were randomized to wound closure with either a small or large tissue bites by lottery method into group A and group B. **Group A (n=40):** abdominal wall closed by Using Small Tissue Bites technique. Small tissue bites were placed at least 5mm from the wound edge 5 mm apart. **In Group B (n=40):** the abdominal wall was closed by using the large tissue bite technique. Large tissue bites were placed 10 mm from the wound edge and 10 mm apart and included only the aponeurosis in the stitches with or without the peritoneum. The demographics and BMI, history of diabetes mellitus, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, hemoglobin, serum albumin, serum bilirubin, blood urea serum creatinine, type of surgery, length of the suture used to close the midline incision and postoperative wound complications such as wound dehiscence and surgical site infection were recorded on Proforma. The length of the wound and suture length to wound length ratio were calculated. Patients were followed up to identify any surgical site infection or wound dehiscence. Patients who developed wound complications during the hospital stay were treated on an individual basis in the form of local wound care and antibiotics as per culture sensitivity.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Age and Sex Distribution

Age Range(years)	Group A (Small Bite)		Group B (large Bite)	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
< 20	4	10	4	10
21-40	9	22.5	9	22.5
41-60	13	32.5	21	52.5
> 61	14	35	6	15
Total	40	100	40	100
Mean \pm SD	47.6 \pm 17.95		47.5 \pm 15.29	
p value	0.8099 (NS)			
Sex Distribution	Group A (Small Bite)		Group B (Large Bite)	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Male	37	92.5	37	92.5
Female	3	7.5	3	7.5
Total	40	100	40	100

Table 2: Wound Site Complications

S. No.	Wound Site Complications	Follow up Period	Group A (Small Bite) (n=6)		Group B (Large Bite) (n=16)		
			Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
1	Surgical Siteinfection	10 Days	5	12.50	13	32.5	
		1 Month	1	2.50	3	7.5	
		3 Months	0	0.00	0	0	
		6 Months	0	0.00	0	0	
	Correlation of duration of presenting complaints in SSI cases						
	Duration of Presenting Complaints/v/s SSI						
	< 3 days		2	33.3	5	31.25	
> 3 days		4	66.7	11	68.75		
p value			0.925 (NS)				
2	Wound dehiscence	10 Days	3	7.50	3	7.5	
		1 Month	1	2.50	2	5	
		3 Months	0	0.00	0	0	
		6 Months	0	0.00	0	0	
	Correlation of duration of presenting complaints in Wound dehiscence						
	Duration of Presenting Complaints v/s Wound dehiscence						
	< 3 days		1	25.0	2	40	
> 3 days		3	75.0	3	60		
p value			0.635 (NS)				
3	Incisional hernia	10 Days	0	0.00	0	0	
		1 Month	0	0.00	0	0	
		3 Months	1	2.50	2	5	
		6 Months	2	5.00	6	15	
	Correlation of duration of presenting complaints in Incisional Hernia						
	Duration of Presenting Complaints/v/s Incisional hernia						
	< 3 days		0	0.0	2	25	
> 3 days		3	100.0	6	75		
p value			0.038				

Table 3: Duration of Hospital Stay

Duration of Hospital Stay(Days)	Group A (Small Bite)		Group B (Large Bite)		P Value
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
< 5 days	21	52.5	17	42.5	0.044(S)
> 5 days	19	47.5	23	57.5	
Total	40	100	40	100	
Mean \pm SD	5.45 \pm 1.35		6.22 \pm 2.18		

Table 4: Ratio of Mean SL to WL

Ratio of meanSL to WL	Group A (Small Bite)		Group B (Large Bite)		P Value
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
< 4.5 : 1	17	42.5	21	52.5	0.3704(NS)
> 4.5 : 1	23	57.5	19	47.5	
Total	40	100	40	100	
Mean \pm SD	4.08 \pm 0.47		3.94 \pm 0.48		

Table 5: Time of Facial Closure

Time of Facial Closure (min.)	Group A (Small Bite)		Group B (Large Bite)		P Value
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
< 10 min.	4	10	32	80	P<0.0001 (S)
> 10	36	90	8	20	
Total	40	100	40	100	
Mean \pm SD	12.8 \pm 1.86		9.25 \pm 1.48		

Discussion

In our study mean age in Group A (Small Bite) is 47.6 \pm 17.95 years and in Group B (Large Bite) 47.5 \pm 15.29 years. When comparing both groups, the p-value was 0.8099, which was not statistically significant. Similar findings was also observed in the study of Dogra V et al. (2022) [13] the mean age in Group I (Large tissue bite) was 49.48 \pm 17.67 years and the mean age in Group II (small tissue bites) was 48.24 \pm 17.46 years. Also in the study of Hassan Y et al. (2018) [14] the mean age was 47.43 \pm 18.49 (large tissue bite) and the mean age in the was 48.09 \pm 18.26 years (small tissue bites). No statistically significant differences were found in the age distribution between the two groups. In our study out of 40 patients, 37 male and 3 female, in Group A and Group B respectively. In a study by Hassan Y et al. (2021) [15] there were 84.56% male and 15.43% females. (Table 1)

In the present study, 6 patients in Group A, 16 patients in Group B developed SSI. When comparing both groups, the p-value was 0.910, which was not statistically significant. In the study by Hassan Y et al. (2021) [15], 24 (19.67%) and 72 (35.64%) patients in small and large bite groups respectively developed surgical site infection. In a study by Kumar A et al. (2022) [16], SSI was present in 7 cases (28%) in the small bite and SSI was present in 13 cases (52%) in the large bite group. In the present study, wound dehiscence developed in 4 patients (10%) in Group A and in 5 patients (12.5%) in Group B who developed wound dehiscence. When comparing both groups, the p-value was 0.630, which was not statistically significant. In the study

by Hassan Y et al. (2021) [15], wound dehiscence occurred in 9 (7.38%) patients in the small bite group and surgical site infection in 22 (10.89%) patients in the large bite group. In a study by Sharma R et al. (2020) [17] in the small bite group, wound dehiscence was present in 4 cases and in the large bite group, SSI was present in 5 cases (n=20), which is similar to our study results. In the study of Kumar A et al. (2022) [16] they observed that in small bite group wound dehiscence was present in 2 cases (8%) and in large bite group wound dehiscence was present in 5 cases (12%) which is similar to our study results.

Incisional hernia developed in 3 patients in Group A, while there were 8 patients in Group B developed incisional hernia. When comparing both groups, the p-value was 0.782, which was not statistically significant. Deerenberg EB et al. (2015) [12] they observed that in small bite group incisional hernia was present in 35 cases (13%), (n=268) and in large bite group, wound dehiscence was present in 57 cases (21%) (n=277), which is similar to our study results. In a study by Chatterjee S et al. (2021) [18], it was observed that in the small bite group, incisional hernia was present in 4 cases (7.8%), and in the large bite group, wound dehiscence was present in 11 cases (20.7%), which is similar to our study results. In a study by Kumar A et al. (2022) [16], they observed that in small bite group incisional hernia was present in 4 cases (16%) (n=18) and in large bite group, wound dehiscence was present in 5 cases (20%), which is similar to our study results (Table 2).

In Group A, the ratio of mean SL to WL was less

than or equal to 4.5: 1 it was in 17 cases (42.5%) and in Group B, it was in 21 cases (52.5%), while In Group B, the ratio of mean SL to WL was more than 4.5: 1 it was in 23 cases (57.5%) and in Group B, it was in 19 cases (47.5%), and the p-value was 0.3704, which was not statistically significant in our study. In a study by Kumar N et al. (2022) [19] In Group A, ratio of mean SL to WL was less than or equal to 4.5: 1 it was in 120 cases (n=200) and 128 cases (n=200) in group B, which is similar to our study results. In a study by Dogra V et al. (2022) [13] ratio of mean SL to WL was less than or equal to 4.5: 1 it was in 71 cases (n=150), and in Group B it was in 85 cases (n=150), which is also similar to our study. (Table 4)

In Group A, time of fascial closure less than and equal to 10 minutes it was in 4 cases (10%) and in Group B it was in 32 cases (80%) and In Group A, time of fascial closure more than 10 minutes it was in 36 cases (90%) and in Group B it was in 8 cases (20%), The mean time in small bite group was 12.8±1.86 and in large bite group it was 9.25±1.48 mins.

The p-value was 0.0138, which was statistically significant in our study. Similar results were observed in the study by Deerenberg EV et al. (2015) [12], who noted that the mean fascial closure time was 14 min for small bites and 10 min for large bites. In the study by Albertsmeier M et al. (2021) [10], the mean fascial closure time was 14.9 min in small bite and in large bite it was 9.3 mins, which is also similar to our study. (Table 5)

Conclusion

The study concluded that the small bites suture technique offers several significant advantages over the large bite suture technique for fascial closure in midline abdominal incision in terms of post-operative complications such as Surgical Site infection, Wound Dehiscence, Incisional Hernia, post-operative pain and duration of hospital stay. These findings are consistent with those of previous studies, suggesting that the small bite technique is better than the large bite suture technique for fascial closure of midline abdominal incisions in patients undergoing emergency laparotomy for peptic perforation peritonitis. Further long-term studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to validate these results and explore the broader applicability of small bites suture techniques in different patient populations.

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